

Review on Animal Behavior Classification using Deep learning

Nitesh Gupta*, Rakesh Kumar **

*Research Scholar, Computer Science & Engineering Department, RNTU, Bhopal, M.P., India

**Associate Professor, Computer Science & Engineering Department, RNTU, Bhopal, M.P., India

Abstract—The ability to quickly, reliably, and accurately measure animal behavior has been made possible by recent developments in computer vision. India has a long history of documented observations on animal behavior. The ancient Indian texts detail the observation and description of animal behavior. Pose estimation, the process of accurately capturing an animal's posture, has been making great strides recently due to advancements in deep learning. Moreover, across many areas, including cyber security, bioinformatics, medical information processing, image detection and recognition, robotics and control, and natural language processing, deep learning has outperformed popular Machine learning methods.

Index Terms— Animal behavior, Computer vision, Pose estimation, Deep learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Recorded observations on animal behavior in India date back to ancient times. Behavior of various animals observed and described in ancient Indian classics. The study of animal behavior is a multifaceted discipline with significant implications for ecology, conservation, and animal welfare. Comprehending animal behavior within their surroundings can enhance our understanding of their ecology, connections, and physiological evolution. In recent years, a number of technological advancements have been of great assistance to the field of study known as collective animal behavior[19].

The accessibility of economical video cameras and the advancement of deep learning algorithms enable researchers to gather and analyse extensive images for the identification and measurement of behavior. This could transform animal behavior studies by offering novel insights that were previously challenging or unachievable.

Deep learning facilitates the acquisition of very accurate models of animals in groups [26]. Very accurate animal grouping models can be created using deep learning models[26]. The application of these models is still unclear, though. This article suggests a deep learning approach that deep learning to identify the missing elements in the data that don't have clear functional conclusions [25,28]. While the deep learning-derived components may have many expressive

features, they only have a small number of input and output variables. For behavioral studies [24] and many more, it is crucial to understand how animals behave and move in their natural habitats. Wildlife management and conservation efforts focus significantly on research into animal behavior. At least \$75 billion is spent annually on environmental protection [22].

Figure 1: Bar graph of animal behavior research articles published yearly

The study of animal behavior is particularly significant in terms of gaining an understanding of the requirements and requirements of animals. Video footages, which a significant advantage given the variety of behaviors that animals exhibit and the fact that behaviors can develop and change in a matter of seconds [1]. In addition, we are able to analyse and identify changes in the animal's location by utilising pose estimation and localising keypoints[11]. This allows us to better interpret the animal's movements and behaviors.

Deep learning-based tracking of multiple animals is a difficult but important job that has many uses in farming, conservation, and agriculture. The main goals are to keep an eye on the health of livestock, protect rare species, and automatically spot animal habits. The task requires two steps: finding where each animal is and following it across a series of movie frames. Even so, tracking animals in complicated situations can still be challenging because they move quickly and in similar ways. This is called shadowing. Standard ways of tracking animals don't work well enough for real-life situations because they are too slow and don't work accurately enough. In the past few years, deep learning has made wonderful progress in tracking various animals by using deep neural networks to pull out

features. The article gives an in-depth look at how different methods for tracking multiple animals have changed and been used over the last five years. These methods are grouped by the tracking concepts they use and can be used for a wide range of animal types, including farm animals and wild animals. Present research based on different animal tracking methods that are based on different tracking models and list their pros and cons when it comes to animal subjects [1]. Hidden Markov models have been demonstrated to be effective in representing animal behavior as a sequence of states. The evaluation indicates that the model predicts animal behavior with an average accuracy of 83.86%. Additionally, a domain expert confirmed the stationary distributions of the resultant models. Cluster analysis was conducted via standard clustering algorithms utilizing the approximation of KL divergence. The clustering generates significant outcomes and categorizes animals into understandable groupings [2]. Using six-degree-of-freedom movement sensors attached to the collars and harnesses of forty-five medium to large-sized dogs, researchers recorded data on seven dynamic and static canine activities: sitting, standing, lying down, trotting, walking, playing, and sniffing for treats. Fifteen canines underwent the same collection procedure [27]. About three minutes elapsed for each of the seven actions. The order of the tasks changed for each of the seventeen canines and for both of their repetitions. Using video recordings taken at one-second intervals by two camcorders during the tests, the actions were annotated retrospectively. The raw data from the movement sensors perfectly synced with the annotations. At first, the seven behaviors were classified using the annotated data to train machine learning algorithms for behavior categorization [3]. Video recordings are crucial for quantifying natural behavior in ethological studies. Inferring kinematic body keypoints through markerless posture estimation algorithms is a significant advancement towards this goal. The following behavior quantification stage is 12. Using these traits to organize and interpret behavioral segments into states. This study introduces a new deep learning toolkit to achieve this goal. Here they present OpenLabCluster, which groups segments based on kinematic body keypoints and uses active learning to improve and classify them into behavioral states. The active learning strategy uses semi-supervised deep learning to select typical instances of segments for annotation, which informs clustering and classification of all segments. OpenLabCluster 19 uses these approaches to organize behavioral segments more efficiently and accurately, despite a limit number of annotations. Here it shows that OpenLabCluster outperforms existing approaches in clustering and classification on four datasets of animal species demonstrating natural behaviors, even with all segments annotated. OpenLabCluster, an open-source interactive graphic interface, provides functions for clustering and classification, notifies scientists of outcomes, and incorporates their choices in further steps [4, 10]. Comprehending animal behavior is crucial for several applications. Nonetheless, current animal behavior datasets exhibit constraints in several dimensions, including a restricted number of animal classes, data samples, and assigned tasks, as well as limited variability

in environmental conditions and perspectives. To mitigate these restrictions, they develop a comprehensive and varied dataset, Animal Kingdom, which offers numerous annotated tasks to facilitate a deeper comprehension of natural animal behaviors. The wild animal footage in our collection captures various times of day across a wide array of environments, featuring differences in backgrounds, perspectives, lighting, and weather conditions. Our dataset comprises 50 hours of annotated videos for localizing pertinent animal behavior segments in lengthy videos for the video grounding task, 30,000 video sequences for the fine-grained multi-label action recognition task, and 33,000 frames for the pose estimation task, encompassing a diverse array of 850 species across six principal animal classes. This study [23] also covers the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and other models and algorithms for object recognition and image categorization. A study shows that picture recognition technology has a lot of promise for making animal behavior research more efficient, safer, and more accurate by using real-world case studies and experimental data. Finally, this work emphasizes the importance of working together across different fields and how new technology can greatly impact protecting the environment and finding animals, as it discusses current challenges and future opportunities in technology. The algorithm examines a compelling aspect of animal behavior, concentrating on the territorial conduct of solitary predators instead of the herding behavior exhibited by some species. To accurately simulate how tigers mark their hunting areas, we need to include more factors like mating seasons, reproduction, and the differences in territories between male and female tigers, but the early results in this paper are either slightly better or at least as good as those from K-means clustering. The approach appears to perform exceptionally well with high-dimensional datasets and those requiring the identification of several clusters [6]. They developed a new method, SUBTLE (spectrogram-UMAP-based temporal-link embedding), which analyzes 3D action skeletons to understand similar behaviors. They develop a temporal proximity index (TPI) as a novel metric to evaluate temporal representation inside the behavioral embedding space in order to identify the optimal embedding strategy. The approach attains the highest TPI score in comparison to existing embedding solutions. The spectrogram-based UMAP cluster detects subtle inter-group distinctions and aligns with human-annotated labels. SUBTLE framework automatically identifies behaviors like walking, grooming, standing, and rearing, and also profiles individual behavior traits, including subtle differences between groups based on age [7]. This paper presents DeepHL, a deep learning-enhanced platform for the comparative analysis of animal movement data, specifically trajectories. This program employs a deep neural network utilizing an attention mechanism to autonomously identify segments in trajectories that are indicative of a specific group. This process emphasizes certain segments within visualized trajectories, allowing biologists to concentrate on these areas and assisting them in uncovering the underlying significance of the highlighted segments to aid in the formulation of novel hypotheses [8]. They proposed a technique for categorizing kitty behavior with DeepLabCut. DeepLabCut can effectively

track feature points regardless of shadows or lighting conditions. The standard methods, including backdrop subtraction and frame subtraction, have been confirmed to be inadequate for accurately recognizing moving objects [9]. Here the author develops a system for recognizing, classifying, and monitoring animal behavior via a smart collar device equipped with inertial sensors and a feed-forward neural network or Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) to categorize potential animal behaviors based on the gathered sensory data. Experimental findings from the horse gait case study indicate that the recognition system attains an accuracy of up to 95.6% [10]. Here the author develops a system for recognizing, classifying, and monitoring animal behavior via a smart collar device equipped with inertial sensors and a feed-forward neural network or Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) to categorize potential animal behaviors based on the gathered sensory data. Experimental findings from the horse gait case study indicate that the recognition system attains an accuracy of up to 95.6% [11]. Quantitative behavioral measurements are essential for addressing enquiries throughout scientific disciplines, ranging from neurology to ecology. Cutting-edge deep-learning techniques significantly enhance data quality and detail by enabling researchers to automatically ascertain the positions of an animal's bodily parts from photos or videos. Nonetheless, existing animal pose estimate techniques exhibit constraints in both speed and robustness. This document presents a user-friendly software toolkit, DeepPoseKit, which resolves these issues with an efficient multi-scale deep-learning model, termed Stacked DenseNet, and a rapid GPU-based peak-detection algorithm for estimating keypoint locations with subpixel accuracy. These advancements enhance processing speed by almost 20% without compromising accuracy relative to existing methods. Here they demonstrate the adaptability of our approaches through many demanding animal pose estimate tasks in both laboratory and field environments, including interactions among groups of individuals. Our efforts diminish obstacles to utilizing modern technologies for behavioral measurement and possess extensive relevance across the behavioral sciences [12]. This paper reviews recent deep learning-enabled greenhouse computer vision developments. First, a brief introduction to deep learning and computer vision. Then they examine over 100 greenhouse studies that have used these technologies for growth monitoring, disease detection, yield calculation, and more up to the present. This article reviews published methodologies, data sets, models, and final performance scores in academic journals. Tables and figures display recent research and practical applications. Key difficulties include model adaptability, computational restrictions, multi-modal sensor fusion, and a lack of tagged greenhouse data [13].

Using deep learning to study animal behavior creates new ways of doing research, which might lead to better health outcomes for people and animals [6]. Acute seizures, morphine withdrawal, nicotine withdrawal, and many more animal disease models can be greatly improved by the capacity to detect and examine particular behaviors, such as rats trembling like a wet dog [21].

Figure 2: Sample of Dog different behavior[17]

The abstraction of human conduct is significantly more complex than that of an animal residing in a confined environment. These kinds of animals possess limited capabilities [16]. These movements occur due to the animal's hunger, thirst, behavioral responses to other animals, or environmental factors.

II. RELATED WORK

Deep learning-based tracking of multiple animals is a difficult but important job that has many uses in farming, conservation, and agriculture. The main goals are to keep an eye on the health of livestock, protect rare species, and automatically spot animal habits. The task requires two steps: finding where each animal is and following it across a series of movie frames. Even so, tracking animals in complicated situations can still be challenging because they move quickly and in similar ways. This is called shadowing. Standard ways of tracking animals don't work well enough for real-life situations because they are too slow and don't work accurately enough. In the past few years, deep learning has made wonderful progress in tracking various animals by using deep neural networks to pull out features. The article gives an in-depth look at how different methods for tracking multiple animals have changed and been used over the last five years. These methods are grouped by the tracking concepts they use and can be used for a wide range of animal types, including farm animals and wild animals. Present research based on different animal tracking methods that are based on different tracking models and list their pros and cons when it comes to animal subjects [1].

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enables the community to develop, adapt, and assess diverse, sophisticated methodologies for analyzing animal behavior. Additionally, here they present a Collaborative Action Recognition (CARE) model that acquires both general and specialized properties for recognizing actions involving previously unencountered animals [5]. This study [23] also covers the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and other models and algorithms for object recognition and image categorization.

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They introduce an innovative dataset for the identification of animal behaviour, gathered in situ using video captured by drones operating above the Mpala Research Centre in Kenya. Videos captured by DJI Mavic 2S drones obtained at 5.4K resolution following IACUC regulations and analysed to identify and monitor each animal inside the frames. A subregion of the image, centred on each animal, was removed and sequentially concatenated to create a "mini-scene." Each frame of every mini-scene was carefully annotated for behavior by a team of annotators under the supervision of a professional behavioural ecologist. The labelled miniscenes constitute our behavior dataset, comprising over 10 hours of annotated films featuring reticulated giraffes, plains zebras, and Grevy's zebras, and spanning seven categories of animal behavior along with an extra category for occlusions. Benchmark outcomes for cutting-edge behavioral recognition architectures indicate a labelling accuracy of 61.9% for macro-

average (per class) and 86.7% for micro-average (per instance). Our dataset enhances current extensive and varied animal behavior collections, as well as smaller, specialised datasets, by being gathered in-situ and by drones, both of which are crucial for the advancement of animal behavior research [14].

Table 1: Summary of Literature

Authors	Year of Publication	Methodology	Dataset
Yeqiang Liu et al.[1]	2024	Object detection, tracking algorithms	Animal tracking datasets
T. Balch et al.[2]	2006	Electromagnetic methods with machine learning	Various datasets from robot swarm simulations and real-world animal movement studies
Antti Vehkaoja et al. [3]	2022	Machine learning algorithms	Movement sensor dataset
Jingyuan Li et al. [4]	2022	Clustering and classification approach	Animal behavior video datasets
X. L. Ng, K. E. Ong et al. [5]	2022	Deep learning techniques	Animal Kingdom dataset
M. Trzciński et al.[6]	2022	Clustering algorithm	Synthetic and real-world datasets
J. Kwon et al. [7]	2024	Unsupervised learning framework	Proprietary animal behavior video datasets
Takuya Maekawa et al. [8]	2020	DeepHL(Deep learning-assisted platform	Tested on trajectories of various animals

This paper presents a pipeline strategy for the fast development of predictive behavioral models utilising a convergence of machine learning technologies[18]. They assessed the accuracy of model's predictions and its importance in comparison to a more established time-series analysis statistical model. The testing outcomes of our proposed pipeline indicated that the LSTM network, trained on JAABA-annotated frames of animal behavior and classifier function results, surpassed the ARIMA model, achieving a markedly lower MSE for behavioral predictions of *Drosophila melanogaster* from three to ten seconds ahead [19]. Opportunities to capitalise on the advantages presented by big data are ubiquitous. By establishing effective pipelines and frameworks for managing data of this magnitude and intricacy, here jointly reduce the barriers to accessing the potential insights that lie ahead [15].

III. DATASETS

It is important to comprehend animal behavior for a variety of reasons. Existing datasets on animal behavior, however, are constrained in a number of ways, such as the number of animal classes, data samples, and tasks available, as well as the limited range of environmental conditions and perspectives. In

order to overcome these constraints, they develop Animal Kingdom, a sizable and varied dataset that offers a variety of annotated activities to facilitate a deeper comprehension of the behaviors of real animals. The footage of wild animals utilised in our collection captures a wide variety of locations with varying backgrounds, perspectives, lighting, and weather conditions at various times of the day. The internet, homes, and zoos are some of the places where these datasets can be found. Some example datasets are shown below.

SPOT-10 (Animal Pattern Benchmark Dataset for Machine Learning Algorithms): The SPOTS-10 dataset is a comprehensive compilation of greyscale images exhibiting various patterns across ten animal species. SPOTS-10 comprises 50,000 greyscale images of size 32×32 , categorised into ten distinct groups, each containing 5,000 images. The training dataset consists of 40,000 photos, while the testing dataset includes 10,000 images. The SPOTS-10 dataset is freely available on the project GitHub page: <https://github.com/amotica/spots-10> by cloning the repository.

Animal-10N Dataset: The ANIMAL-10N collection comprises 5 pairs of perplexing animals, totaling 55,000 pictures. The five couples are as follows: (cat, lynx), (jaguar, cheetah), (wolf, coyote), (chimpanzee, orangutan), (hamster, guinea pig).

The images are sourced from several internet search engines, including Bing and Google, using predefined labels as search keywords. Images were classified by 15 recruited participants (10 undergraduates and 5 graduate students); each participant annotated a total of 6,000 images, with 600 images per class.

Upon the elimination of extraneous images, the training dataset comprises 50,000 images, while the test dataset consists of 5,000 images. The noise rate (mislabeling ratio) of the dataset is around 8%.

CIFAR-10: The CIFAR-10 dataset comprises 60,000 32×32 color images categorized into 10 classes, with 6,000 images in each class. There are 50,000 training photos and 10,000 test images.

The dataset has five training batches and one test batch, each containing 10,000 photos. The test batch has precisely 1000 randomly selected photographs from each category. The training batches consist of the remaining photos arranged in a random sequence; nevertheless, certain batches may include a greater number of images from one class compared to others. The training batches comprise precisely 5000 images from each category.

Stanford Dogs Dataset: The Stanford Dogs collection includes images of 120 dog breeds globally. This dataset has been constructed with images and annotations from ImageNet for the purpose of fine-grained image categorisation. The data was first gathered for detailed image classification, a complex issue due to the similarity in characteristics across some dog breeds, as well as variations in colour and age.

The Oxford-IIIT Pet Dataset: The Oxford-IIIT Pet Dataset comprises 37 categories of pets, with around 200 photos per class, developed by the Visual Geometry Group at Oxford.

The images exhibit significant changes in scale, position, and lighting. Each image is accompanied by a corresponding ground truth annotation detailing breed, head region of interest (ROI), and pixel-level trimap segmentation.

Table 1: List of animal behavior dataset

Dataset Name	Number of classes	Total Number of images	Split Ratio	Training Images	Testing Images
SPOTS-10	10	50,000	80:20	40,000	10,000
ANIMAL-10N	10	55,000	90:10	50,000	5,000
CIFAR-10	10	60,000	80:20	50,000	10,000
Dog Breed Classification Dataset	120	10,222	70:30	70,111	3,111
The Oxford-IIIT Pet Dataset	37	7,400	80:20	5,920	1,480
Mammal Club	15	80,099	70:30	64,079	16,020

IV. CONCLUSION

Using computer vision technology, this study surveys current methods for tracking many animals. It evaluates the strengths and limitations of several animal tracking methodologies and covers datasets, applications, and concerns in this area. Our survey highlights the unique challenges of tracking multiple species, namely the similarity in appearances and the complexity of their movement patterns, which makes traditional tracking systems difficult to use.

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Authors

Nitesh Gupta is a Ph.D. scholar in the Department of Computer Science Engineering from Rabindranath Tagore University Bhopal (M.P). He completed his Master of Engineering (Computer Science & Engineering) from LNCT, Bhopal in 2009. His interests include Database Technologies, Image Processing, Security Analytics, Network security

, Artificial Intelligence, and Machine Learning. He has experience is about 15 years of experience in teaching and Research at the college and University level. He has organized many Trainings and Workshops. He has published many Research papers in Reputed Journals (i.e., SCOPUS and UGC Approved) and presented many papers in various National and International Conferences.

Dr. Rakesh Kumar is an Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science & Engineering from Rabindranath Tagore University Bhopal (M.P). And Head, Centre for IoT & Advance Computing. He is member of Institute Innovation Council (IIC) MHRD and the Innovation Ambassador at University. He completed his Ph.D. in Computer Science & Engineering. His area interests include IoT, IoE, Software Engineering, Operating System, Database Technologies, Data Structures, Data Mining, Data Warehousing, Robotics, Drone Technology, Artificial Intelligence and Computer Architecture. He has experience is about 17 years of experience of teaching and Research at college and University level. He has organized many Trainings and Workshops. He has delivered many Expert Lectures in various organizations. He has organized AICTE funded FDP. He has guided various Projects at State and National Level competitions. He is working on various funded projects. He has published many Research papers in Reputed Journals (i.e., SCI, SCOPUS and UGC Approved) and presented many papers in various National and International Conferences. He is the author of Book Chapters and Patents. He has appointed as an Editorial board member and reviewer in various Journals, International conferences. He was recognize by "Quarterly Franklin Membership" (Membership ID#VY34049), London Journal of Engineering Research (LJER), London Journals Press (UK) for research paper "Inside Agile Family Software Development Methodologies. He is the founder member of Centre for IoT & Advance Computing.